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Conflict And Political Instability In Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

This paper examined the phenomenon of conflict and political instability in Rivers State. The paper further investigated the underlining factors and impact of conflict and political instability, and proffers policy remedy to the incessant conflict and political instability in the state. The paper adopted the social structure and anomie theory while the survey research design was used. Data were analysed using the simple percentage statistical method. Findings reveal that cultism and cult-related violence, oil theft, artisanal refining, chieftaincy tussle, political greed and battle for supremacy and control were significant factors that engendered conflict and political instability in Rivers State. Also, loss of revenue, economic hardship, loss of lives and property, unhealthy inter-ethnic rivalry and relocation of people and business activities were impact of conflict and political instability. The paper recommended among others that the state should improve the socioeconomic state of the people, prosecute criminals and offenders of the laws and strengthen the e-voting system to get rid of political conflict.

Keywords: Conflict, Political Instability, Cultism, Ethnicity, Oil theft

INTRODUCTION

Conflicts are common and unavoidable in all human society. All over the world, conflicts occur because society is made up of people with differing interests and values (Afegbua, 2010). The issue of conflict and political instability in Africa, according to Adeyeri (2013) will continue to dominate political discourse by both academics and non-academics. Africa, the second largest continent in the world, has passed and is still passing through several restless stages. The nature of political power in many African states, together with the real and perceived consequences of capturing and maintaining power is a key source of conflict and political instability across the continent. It is frequently the case that political victory assumes a “winner-takes-all” form with respect to wealth and resources, patronage, and the prestige and prerogatives of office (Arriola, 2009).

To-date, the country is still haunted by historical injustices and oppressive structures that were bequeathed to the post-colonial leadership. This is an aspect that informs the weak institutions of the state, flawed legislative systems and constant struggles for political power to the detriment of the well-being of many nations, which could have moved on a path of development as part of modern societies. It was Ake (1995) who painted a gloomy picture of the African continent saying: “most of Africa is not developing”. This apt description of the decline in nearly all African countries underscores the depth of underdevelopment ravaging the people in the midst of abundant natural resources. Ake (1995) locates the genesis of this problem in the inclement political and social conditions in the developing countries. This manifests in poor planning and implementation, lack of entrepreneurial abilities, the stifling of market forces, falling commodity prices and unfavourable terms of trade, poverty of ideas, the dependency syndrome, corruption and indiscipline. The Nigerian State is a victim of conflict, political instability and a cyclical legitimacy crisis. The country’s authoritarian leadership faced a legitimacy crisis, political intrigues, in an

ethnically-differentiated polity, where ethnic competition for resources drove much of the pervasive corruption and profligacy (Fagbadebo, 2007). Nigeria's political instability is conventionally attributed to the manner in which leaders sustain themselves in power. Leaders across the country hold onto office by purchasing support through the distribution of state resources; as such, any conflict over their allocation is thought to degenerate into a struggle over control of the state. Violence erupts either because some elites crave a larger share of the spoils controlled by the leader or because those outside the leader's patronage-based coalition want access to resources to which they have been denied (Annan, 1998).

Among the largest of the oil-producing Nigerian states, Rivers had been at the heart of the Niger Delta militancy until 2009. Now, the state remains beset with a different array of political, communal, and criminal issues, including cult and gang-related violence, protests, and kidnappings. Rivers is a pivotal state in Nigeria general elections and has experienced an elevated risk of election-related violence from 2014 till date. Since May 2013, political tensions have been high in Rivers State after the disputed Nigerian Governor's Forum election that saw Governor Amaechi emerged. Other issues were issues of cross-carpet by the then Governor, the zoning formula in the state and associated ethnic sentiments across zoning areas. The results of the November 2014 PDP primary elections and the disenfranchisement of certain ethnic groups. Following these results, the Movement for the Survival of the Ogoni People (MOSOP) made the announcement that it would form an "indigenous authority" independent of the state and federal government. Also of note, another former militant group, the Movement for the Emancipation of the Niger Delta (MEND) apparently made a statement endorsing the opposition candidate in the general election after claiming dissatisfaction with the then PDP led administration. The aim of this paper therefore is to examine conflict and the various dimensions of political instability in Nigeria with a focus on Rivers State, 2015 to 2023. The specific objectives are to:

- a. examine the factors that are responsible for conflict and political instability in Rivers State,
- b. investigate the impact of conflict on political instability in Rivers State, and
- c. identify policy remedy to conflict and political instability in Rivers State.

Theoretical Framework

Social Structure and Anomie theory: The theory tries to establish relationship between structural bottleneck and anomie, as well as criminal tendency. The concept of anomie was developed by Durkheim to explain deviance in human society. Anomie signifies a moral breakdown in the rules or norms that govern individuals in the society. As such, when there are no clear rules to guide members of the society, individuals find it difficult to adjust to the changing conditions of life. This in turn, leads to frustration, conflict, dissatisfaction and deviance. Durkheim concludes that, crime or deviance is inevitable in a period of rapid socioeconomic change.

The theory of anomie is taken further by Merton in 1938. Merton's idea of anomie is with regards to the strain that is imposed on certain individuals by the social structure. Merton begins by saying that society defines being successful in terms of certain goals (such as financial security) but does not always provide the means (including schooling and good jobs) to reach these cultural expectations. Thus, criminal behaviour is a manifestation of the mismatch between societal goal and the institutional means of achieving them. Therefore, patterns of rule breaking depend on whether or not people accept society's goals and whether or not they have the opportunity to reach them. To this extent, five adaptations are bound to emerge. The modes of adaptations include: conformity, innovation, retreatism, ritualism, and rebellion.

Conformity is non-deviant because the people that fell under its category accept both the culturally defined goals and the structurally condoned means of achieving the goals. Innovation involves those individuals, who accept goals but reject the means, retreatism represents people who reject both goals and means, ritualism is for those who reject the goals but accept the means, and rebellion is the act of those who try to change the entire system. Sztompka (2003) also opines that Merton's structural analysis is understood as a condition of dissociation between uniform cultural demands of success and the differentiated opportunities for success. It is in such a condition that, anomie generates these various

forms of deviant conduct. The theory made a significant contribution towards explaining why criminal activities are becoming inevitable under social arrangements that design hard-earned values, a situation that drift some people to violence, for example insurgency in Nigeria. According to the theory, society creates strain on some individuals by making it difficult or rather impossible to achieve the societal goal using approved means. These unfavoured, stressed individuals include armed bandits who resort to violence and criminality to achieve the desired societal goal. This scenario is evident in Northwestern Nigeria, as widespread poverty, unemployment and social inequality is increasingly linked with emerging crimes like armed banditry. Most of these unknown groups of armed youths engage in abduction of rural settlers, travellers and students in exchange for huge amount of ransom. While Merton's theory is arguable the most frequently adopted criminological theory to explain rationale for crime in Nigeria, the theory has its shortcomings. Tierney (2006) argued that it is unclear why some individuals opt for one type of adaptation rather than another.

Concept of Conflict

There have been numerous efforts at defining conflicts and description such as "armed conflict" violent conflicts abounds in development literature. More generic definitions often overlap with violence and present conflict as hostilities leading to the use of physical force or power, threatened action against another person, or against a group or community that either results in or has a high likelihood of resulting in injury, death, psychological harm, mal-development or deprivation. (Wito, 2000). Imobighe (2003) argues that conflict represents a condition of disharmony within an interaction process usually as a result of a clash of interests between the parties involved in some form of relationship. Burge (1921) argues that conflict is designed to resolve divergent dualism (and achieve) some kinds of unity even if it be through the annihilation of one of the conflicting parties. Scholars like Wilson and Kolb (1947) sees conflict as a negative totality as dysfunctional or destructive process and the breakdown of communication. Stedimon (1991), notes that conflicts result from human interaction in the context of incompatible ends where one's ability to satisfy needs or ends depends on the choices, decisions and behaviour of others. Zartman (1991) sees conflict as the violent exhibition or expression of incompatibility" though conflicts may become violent according to Sedman (1991) violence is not an inherent aspect of conflict but rather a potential form that conflict may take". Jonathan et al (2003) defined conflict as a contested incompatibility that concerns government or territory of both where the use of armed forces between two parties results in at least battle related-deaths. Dudley (1999) also came up with a similar observation of conflict. According to him, conflict is an inescapable part of our daily lives, an inevitable result of our highly complex, competitive and often litigious society.

From the above analyses, it is clear that conflict is a behavioural pattern involving two or more individual ties, which can be inter-personalities, inter-groups, inter-organizations and inter-states. Another concept central to this discourse is sectionalism. The attribute of sectional behaviour is exclusiveness and the pursuit of parochial interest. Here, there is an intense struggle for separateness. This may lead to discriminatory practices in all facets of life. Since conflict itself cannot be ruled out in a society, the coming together of different ethnic groups brings conflict.

Concept of Political Instability

Political instability takes a variety of forms, such as cult groups, communal violence, rural insurgency, urban riots, coups d'état, and civil wars. However, this paper generalizes the use of these terms at various context. According to Adeyeri (2013), political instability arises as a result of the inability of government and the society in general to adequately address the grievances of the population or particular subset of that population. The source of grievances can be internal, external or political depending on the circumstances (Ofiaga, 2011). He stated further that in such situation, patterns of conflicts or interaction also become more complex. Egobueze (2013) opines that political instability in Nigeria stems from the inability of its bourgeoisie to take control over other classes in the struggle to create a viable hegemony in the social formation. Political instability needs to be better understood and disaggregated into its various

forms, because discontent alone, however, does not necessarily generate political instability, individual and mechanisms must be present to articulate the grievances and mobilise the aggrieved to demand redress from government, as tensions mount within a society. Political instability is unconstitutional change of government, either regular or irregular change of government. It is a situation whereby a country is going through political turmoil. Given their encyclopaedic work on political events in Africa, Morrison, Mitchell and Paden (1989) observe that other manifestations of instability are often a response on the part of communal groups in national populations to elite instability which either fails to bring about a reapportionment of ethnic representation in government or a redistribution of other goods.

However, Rivers State has been adjudged the heart of Nigeria’s booming oil industry, and its government is one of the wealthiest state administrations in Nigeria. Due to rising oil prices, Rivers State government now earns roughly four times the annual revenues it saw in 1999, and at the local government level revenues have increased tenfold. Crime and political violence have both grown in stride with the Niger Delta’s colossal failures of governance. In Nigeria as a whole, national, state, and local elections since 1999 have been consistently rigged by means of violence and fraud. Polls in Rivers State have been among the most violent and brazenly rigged in the country. There is a direct link between gang violence and the corruption and criminality of many Rivers’ politicians. Many of the state’s disastrously ineffective political leaders have kept themselves in place by violently rigging their own elections, something they have in large part relied on gangs of armed thugs to achieve. The money they use to fund, arm, and support these gangs is generated by the corrupt practices in which these politicians engage. Once in office, they either abandon the well-armed gangs to their own devices or continue using them to intimidate their opponents and carry out lucrative criminal activity such as “oil bunkering”.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research design refers to a frame or plan that is used as a guide in collecting and analysing the data for the study. This work adopts the survey research design which involves qualitative and quantitative data. However, the study adopts the Taro Yamane’s formula to determine the sample of 400 in a projected population of 7,474,973 in Rivers State (NBS, 2019). The simple random sampling technique was adopted to administer one hundred (100) equal number of questionnaires to politicians, community leaders, civil servants and business proprietors. The study used Cronbach’s alpha coefficient to test reliability. The Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) was used to test the Cronbach alpha coefficient reliability, only items that return alpha value of 0.7 and above were considered in this study. The 4-likert scale was used in rating the responses with options of strongly agree (SA), agree (A), disagree (D), and strongly disagree (SD). The responses of the respondents are arranged, grouped, tabulated and analysed using the simple percentage statistical method. This means that the degree of percentage score of one response to another or others will determine the acceptability or rejection of a particular statement or response.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Table 1: Administration of Questionnaires

Number of questionnaires administered	400
Number of properly completed and returned	250
Percentage rate of successfully completed and returned questionnaires	63%

Source: Field Work, 2024

The interpretation of the above is that 400 questionnaires were administered to the various category of respondents. 150 were wrongly filled, mishandled, and destroyed while 250 questionnaires were properly filled, completed and returned representing an acceptance number of 63% which is also a good response rate for this study.

Table 2: Social and Demographic Background of all Respondents

Variables	Categories	Frequency (F)	Percentages (%)
Gender distribution	Male	140	56
	Female	110	44
	Total	250	100
Educational qualifications	FSLC	10	4
	SSCE/ND/NCE	60	24
	HND/BA/B.Sc/PGD	130	52
	MBA/MPA/M.Sc/Ph.D	50	20
	Total	250	100
Category of respondents	Civil servants	50	20
	Politicians	45	18
	Community member	80	32
	Business proprietor	75	30
	Total	250	100

Source: Field Work, 2024.

Table 2 above shows that 140 questionnaires representing 56% were administered to male while 110 questionnaires with 44% were female. This demographic statistics reveals that the staff of the respondents who attended to the questionnaires are mainly males. Notwithstanding, responses from both genders are analysed for a valid judgement.

The table above depicts that 4% of the respondents have FSLC; 60(24%) have SSCE/ND/NCE; 130(52%) respondents possess HND/BA/B.SC/PGD while 50 respondents representing 20% are holders of MBA/MPA/M.SC/Ph.D. This shows that the respondents are dominated by different levels of graduates with various certificate holders. This suggests that the respondents have good knowledge about conflict and political instability in Nigeria.

The table also shows that 50 (20%) of the respondents are civil servants, 45 (18%) of the respondents are politicians, 80 respondents representing 32% are community members while 75 (30%) are business owners.

Table 3: Factors that are responsible for conflict and political instability in Rivers State.

Questionnaires	Strongly Agreed f (%)	Agreed f (%)	Strongly Disagreed f (%)	Disagreed f (%)	Total
Cultism and cult related violence engender political instability.	125 (50%)	52 (21%)	50 (20%)	23 (9%)	250 (100%)
Oil theft and artisanal refining stimulate political instability.	110 (44%)	100 (40%)	10 (4%)	30 (12%)	250 (100%)
Chieftaincy tussles, crude oil related conflicts, and communal crises engender political instability.	130 (52%)	60 (24%)	10 (4%)	50 (20%)	250 (100%)

Source: Field Work, 2024.

Table 3 reveals that out of 250 respondents, 125 (50%) respondents strongly agreed, and 52 (21%) respondents agreed that cultism and cult related violence engender political instability while 50 (20%) respondents strongly disagreed with 23 (9%) respondents disagreed. This indicates that cultism and cult related violence engender political instability.

The table also indicates those 110 (44%) respondents “strongly agreed” and 100 (40%) of the respondents “agreed” that oil theft and artisanal refining stimulate political instability while 10 (4%) “strongly disagreed” and 30 (12%) of the respondents “disagreed” that oil theft and artisanal refining stimulate political instability. This indicates that oil theft and artisanal refining stimulate political instability.

Furthermore, it is observed that 130 respondents representing 52% “strongly agreed” and 60 representing 24% of the respondents and “agreed” that chieftaincy tussles, crude oil related conflicts, and communal crises engender political instability while 10 respondents representing 4% “strongly disagreed” and 50 respondents representing 20% “disagreed”. This implies that chieftaincy tussles, crude oil related conflicts, and communal crises engender political instability.

Table 4: The impact of conflict and political instability in Rivers State

Questionnaires	Strongly Agreed f (%)	Agreed f (%)	Strongly Disagreed f (%)	Disagreed f (%)	Total
Conflict has led to economic hardship in political instability.	95 (38%)	85 (34%)	50 (20%)	20 (8%)	250 (100%)
Unhealthy inter-ethnic rivalry and competition has led to loss of lives and property.	102 (41%)	101 (40%)	37 (15%)	10 (4%)	250 (100%)
Conflict has led to migration of people and their businesses from the state to other peaceful areas.	80 (32%)	95 (38%)	50 (20%)	25 (10%)	250 (100%)

Source: Field Work, 2024.

The table above reveals that 95 respondents representing 38% “strongly agreed” with 85 representing 34% “agreed” that conflict has led to economic hardship in political instability while 50 respondents representing 20% “strongly disagreed” with 20 respondents representing 8% “disagreed” on the claims. This submits that conflict has led to economic hardship in political instability.

Furthermore, investigation reveals that 102 (41%) of the respondents strongly agreed, 101 (40%) of the respondents “agreed” while 37 (15%) “strongly disagreed” and 10 (4%) of the respondents “disagreed” that conflict promotes unhealthy inter-ethnic rivalry and competition in political instability. This implies that conflict promotes unhealthy competition in instability.

On question whether conflict has led to migration of people and their businesses from the state, 80 (32%) respondents “strongly agreed”, 95 (38%) “agreed” while 50 respondents of (20%) “strongly disagreed” and 25 (10%) “disagreed” respectively. This implies that conflict has led to migration of people and their businesses from the state to other peaceful areas.

Table 5: Showing policy remedy to conflict and political instability in Rivers State.

Questionnaires	Strongly Agreed f (%)	Agreed f (%)	Strongly Disagreed f (%)	Disagreed f (%)	Total
Socioeconomic empowerment is a key to ending armed conflict and political instability.	90 (36%)	95 (38%)	45 (18%)	20 (8%)	250 (100%)
Prosecution of law enforcers found to be part of insecurity and conflict.	125 (50%)	52 (21%)	50 (20%)	23 (9%)	250 (100%)
e-voting system should be strengthened	80 (32%)	95 (38%)	50 (20%)	25 (10%)	250 (100%)

Source: Field Work, 2024.

This table above shows that 90 (36%) strongly agreed and 95 (38%) of the respondents disagreed that socioeconomic empowerment is a key to ending armed conflict and political instability while 45 (18%) strongly disagreed and 20 (8%) disagreed that socioeconomic empowerment is a key to ending armed conflict and political instability. This implies that socioeconomic empowerment is a key to ending armed conflict and political instability.

Question whether prosecution of law enforcers found to be part of insecurity and conflict. 125 respondents representing 50% strongly agreed and 52 (21%) agreed that prosecution of law enforcers found to be part of insecurity and conflict. 50 respondents representing 20% strongly disagreed while 23 (9%) disagreed. It can be deduced that prosecution of law enforcers found to be part of insecurity and conflict.

Whether e-voting system should be strengthened. 80 (32%) “strongly agreed” and 95 (38%) of the respondents “agreed” while 50 (20%) “strongly disagreed” and 25 (10%) of the respondents “disagreed” e-voting system should be strengthened. One may be persuaded to agree with respondents who “strongly disagreed” that e-voting system should be strengthened.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Factors that are responsible for conflict and political instability in Rivers State: Data analysis reveals that out of 250 respondents, 177 respondents agreed that cultism and cult related violence engender political instability, 210 respondents “agreed” that oil theft and artisanal refining stimulate political instability while 190 respondents “agreed” that chieftaincy tussles, crude oil related conflicts, and communal crises engender political instability.

The views above are supported by Sofiri, Kiale and Jackson (2022). They claim that the menace of cultism in River State has its origin in the 1990s and early 2000s with the emergence of street gangs in Port Harcourt affiliated to campus-based confraternities such as the Vikings and the Klansmen. During the early days of cultism in Rivers State, the major cult gangs such as the DeyBam and DeyWell had their operational bases in Port Harcourt metropolis and parts of Okrika Local Government Area. Two decades after, a plethora of cult gangs including the Icelanders, Greenlanders, Bobos, Outlaws, etc. as well as female wings of these gangs such as Ice-Queens, Girl-Girls have emerged and permeated the nooks and crannies of the state.

A respondent revealed that:

there is a general perception that the proliferation of grassroots-based armed cult groups and associated violence are the most important security threats to the life, safety, and livelihoods of the people in Rivers State. these groups are sponsored mostly by government officials who use them to gain political popularity (A. Alabo, personal communication, July 19, 2024.)

Furthermore, inter-cult clashes, cult killings, and recently, cult invasion of local communities are fast becoming an integral part of social life in Rivers State, such that it can be argued that cult groups have been let loose in the state with impunity of violence. While the presence of cult groups and cult violence are visible in almost all parts of the state, the study revealed that some LGAs and communities are worse hit than others.

Another respondent revealed that:

is the contest for the occupation of the chieftaincy space in Asama community in Andoni Local Government Area which has exacerbated the crisis of insecurity as aspirants contracted cultists and militants to enhance their competitive advantage. The two dominant factions in the chieftaincy conflict also contracted or aligned with cult groups to intimidate their opponents (P. Nengi, personal communication, July 20, 2024).

Sofiri, Kialeee and Jackson (2022) noted that while one faction aligned with the Icelanders, the other faction stuck with the Movement for the Emancipation of the Niger Delta (MEND) (an amalgamation of other cult groups except for Icelanders, not to be confused with the regional MEND of 2006). Similarly, the factions involved in the chieftaincy crisis in Ngo and Ataba have contracted the two dominant cult groups/militant movements in furtherance of their struggle for the occupation of the chieftaincy space. The area is also reputed for inter-cult conflict for the occupation and control of illicit business spaces such as oil theft, sea piracy, and other criminal activities. The climax of the gang wars was the battle between Icelanders and MEND in which MEND eliminated Icelanders and established its dominance over the area.

Summarily, the study has revealed that political interest of some unscrupulous politicians to gain political popularity, chieftaincy interest, cult groups alignment and control over resources are some of the underlining factors that escalate the unending conflict and political instability in Rivers State.

The impact of conflict and political instability in Rivers State: Investigation reveals that 180 out of 250 respondents agreed that conflict has led to economic hardship in political instability while 203 of the respondents also agreed that conflict promotes unhealthy inter-ethnic rivalry and competition in political instability. 175 respondents agreed that conflict has led to migration of people and their businesses from the state to other peaceful areas.

In line with the above, secondary data reveals that the implications and costs of conflict across the country are multi-dimensional. Afegbua (2010) notes that the implications and costs of conflicts is loss of revenue in the form of tax charges and rates on varied items by local governments cannot be collected during violent crises, implying loss of revenue for development purposes. Corroborating this claim, Sofiri, Kialeee and Jackson (2022) noted that the rise in the oil theft and artisanal refining economy across the state has further compounded the insecurity challenges currently faced in the state. The existing frame of arguments on the prominence of oil theft and artisanal refining in Rivers State is that it produces quick money for the local actors at the expense of public interests (Ezirim, 2018).

An interviewee responded that:

Due to activities of these cult groups, many other criminal gangs arose to start stealing, bugling people's homes, raping and innocent women. This has resulted to a shift or migration from the state to a more peaceful state where small business can thrive. By this, the state has loss substantial revenue to other areas (J. Alatoru, personal communication, July 24, 2024).

Another implication of conflict is the loss of lives. Violent crises in Nigeria have resulted in a number of casualties. Other minor wars in the country have also recorded loss of human lives. Loss of human lives has implications for the nation's economy as the killings have effects on the agile workforce. The Niger-Delta violent conflicts have claimed the lives of hundreds of oil workers and expatriates (O'Neil, 2004). Kidnapping hijacks, and hostage-taking for ransom along the major highways and waterways in the state have increasingly become a recurring feature in the security landscape of the state. In 2019, the state experienced what could be described as a resurgence of cult violence, kidnapping, and armed robbery activities that almost crippled the economy of the state. Most communities in Ikwerre, Ogoni, Andoni, and Emohua were overwhelmed by cult violence and kidnapping. The East-West Road, particularly the Emohua area up to the Rumuekpe Junction, were made impassable due to the activities of armed robbers and kidnapers despite the presence and proximity of heavily armed military and police personnel at various checkpoints on that road. This was also the case with the Elele Alimini axis of the Owerri-Port Harcourt Road where commercial buses filled with passengers were frequently hijacked and passengers abducted. In one case on July 20, 2019, the 16 passengers in a commercial bus returning from Owerri to Port Harcourt were abducted at Emerule-Ubima junction (Ofiebor, 2019). In some cases, the abducted passengers would be raped (Otubor, 2019). This was the pathetic situation of both passengers and commercial drivers on these two major roads before the Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Area

(ONELGA) Security and Peace Advisory Committee (OSPAC), a government-backed local vigilante group emerged to restore order and security.

In another dimension, Amara (n.d) observes that Rivers State has experienced waves of ethnic and communal violence in many parts of the local governments which have caused many lives to be lost and many others internally displaced with their corresponding destruction of properties. Ethnic and communal conflicts are contemporary realities which if not properly addressed at the appropriate time, could lead to outright destruction of the state's image. Issues of loss of lives and property, relocation of industries and ethnic communal rifts are significant traces to political instability in the state.

Policy remedy to conflict and political instability in Rivers State: Investigation reveals that 185 of the respondents agreed that socioeconomic empowerment is a key to ending armed conflict and political instability, 177 agreed that prosecution of law enforcers found to be part of insecurity and conflict should be implemented while e-voting system is strengthened.

It has been identified that socioeconomic improvement is the key to a peaceful society (Sofiri, Kialee and Jackson, 2022).

An interviewee responded that:

The major reason for conflict and political instability is lack of socioeconomic improvement. If everyone is engaged in meaningful socioeconomic activity, nobody will be willing to become a puppet to politician where guns and other violent engagement weapons would be used to cause unrest. This, the politicians are aware of and as such adopt this pattern to subjugate people and score cheap political gain (O. Nkechi, personal communication, July 26, 2024).

In the light of the above, there is an urgent need for community leaders to rebuild community governance institutions to promote transparency and accountability in the management of funds and other benefits accruing to communities. Community leaders have a responsibility to assist the authorities to ensure peace by refusing to allow the establishment of crude oil cooking camps and cult/criminal gangs' operational camps in their communities. Participation is not easy to achieve in communities where there are marked hierarchical relationships. The challenge is to mainstream socially excluded groups in community administration (Egobueze, 2019). Consequently, concerted efforts should be made to promote participatory and inclusive governance by communities' leaders especially, the inclusion of socially disadvantaged groups such as women, youths, and people with disabilities in the decision-making process. Governance by communities' leaders especially, the inclusion of socially disadvantaged groups such as women and youth in the decision-making process should be encouraged.

Contestants for chieftaincy spaces should desist from recruiting and arming community youths and contracting cultists in their struggles for access and control of the chieftaincy space and also demobilize their "private armies" wherever they exist. The wanton destruction of communities, properties, and violation of human rights of communities' people emanated from invitations of "state security forces to maintain law and order". To ensure re-entry and build confidence, oil companies should desist from using and endorsing the heavy-handed military approach to the resolution of communities-companies' disputes. The government must adopt the use of technology particularly drones to conduct security surveillance (Egobueze, 2019).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The problem of insecurity is a consequence of the interplay of a web of political, economic, social, and cultural conditions and processes that generate and sustain violent conflicts in the state. These conflicts may be on a small or large scale; they may occur within and among groups, communities, or organizations; and may be triggered by ethnic, political, or economic differences, or arise from differences in values, beliefs, and attitudes regarding issues. Insecurity in River State has manifested in diverse forms such as political violence, sea piracy, oil theft, and artisanal refining, cultism and related

crimes of kidnapping, armed robbery, arms, and drug trafficking, as well as armed inter/intracommunity conflicts arising from chieftaincy tussles and competition for environmental resources. Increasing political competition in the state and the criminalization of the Niger Delta struggle by militia capitalists created a violent economy where cultists, militants, criminal gangs thrive, and perpetrate acts of criminality and state-sponsored violence for selfish economic and political gains.

Given the above, a psycho-cultural reorientation of the outlook of the state's political class, in particular, is inevitable. The implication here is that there is a need to rehabilitate politics in Rivers State and Nigeria as a moral force for social change and social justice. Besides, the political class must demonstrate the political will to curb the menace of insecurity in the state by dismantling the economy of violence through a genuine effort at discontinuing all forms of rewards and incentives for violence and criminal actors while utilizing the instrumentality of the state to enforce strict sanctions and punishments on criminals, militants, and cultists.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the foregoing, the paper offers the following recommendations.

- a. Socio-economic empowerment is key because the study shows that some of the challenges of insecurity are necessitated by massive youth unemployment and lack of socio-economic development. Consequently, there is an urgent need for the promotion of community development programmes and access to refined petroleum products, especially in coastal communities.
- b. Some of the sponsors of cult and electoral violence have been identified by state security agents yet, the government has not deemed it necessary to bring them to book by charging them to court following the State's Anti-Cult Law and other related statutory laws. There should be no sacred cows in the task of curbing armed violence in Rivers State. Hence, the government and security operatives must strive to be firm at all times and ensure that those found culpable face the law.
- c. The federal government should introduce electronic voting system to minimize or reduce the role and political significance of cult groups in rigging elections in Nigeria. The disengagement of cult groups and cult members from the political and electoral process will diminish political support, backing, and patronage of politicians for the former. INEC is planning to use electronic voting in 2020 in the Edo and Ondo elections. Advocacy must be geared in this direction to pressure INEC to implement electronic voting nationally.

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